

Supporting Information for: Bias-driven conductance increase with length in porphyrin tapes.

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1. Synthesis

General. Unless stated otherwise, all reagents were obtained from commercial sources and used as received without further purification. Toluene were dried over 4 Å molecular sieves, diisopropylamine (DIPA) was freshly distilled over CaH₂. Petroleum ether (PE) of a 40–60 °C boiling point range was used. Compounds **fP2_{Br}** and **fP3_{Br}** (see Figure S1) were prepared according to literature procedures.¹

Figure S1. Molecular structures of the precursor compounds **fP2_{Br}** and **fP3_{Br}**. THS = trihexylsilyl.

Preparation of fP2. The bromoporphyrin dimer **fP2_{Br}** (16.4 mg, 4.7 μmol) and *S*-(4-ethynylphenyl)-thioacetate (4.2 mg, 23 μmol) were dissolved in toluene (10 mL), DIPA (2 mL) was added and the solution was frozen in liquid nitrogen. Afterwards, tetrakis-triphenylphosphine palladium(0) (0.5 mg, 0.4 μmol) and CuI (0.1 mg, 0.5 μmol) were added and the mixture was evacuated. The solution was subjected to three freeze-pump-thaw cycles to exclude dioxygen, after which it was stirred at room temperature for 24 h. The mixture was directly passed over a SiO₂ plug eluted with DCM and the solvents removed. The product was purified by column chromatography (SiO₂, PE/DCM 4/1) and size exclusion chromatography (Biobeads SX-1, toluene + 1% pyridine). Yield: 3.7 mg, 21%. UV-vis

(CHCl₃) λ_{\max} / nm (ϵ / mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹): 1101 (66.3), 964 (35.5), 585 (217), 487 (54.4), 442 (157), 352 (41.8). MS (MALDI-TOF, dithranol) m/z : 3655.3 ([M]⁺ C₂₂₈H₃₅₀N₈O₂S₂Si₈Zn₂ requires 3654.9). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.42 (d, J = 4.6 Hz, 4H), 7.74 (s, 12H), 7.72 – 7.66 (m, 4H), 7.43 (d, J = 4.6 Hz, 4H), 7.42 – 7.38 (m, 4H), 7.03 (s, 4H), 2.39 (s, 6H), 1.40 – 1.10 (m, 192H), 0.86 – 0.69 (m, 120H).

Preparation of fp3. The bromoporphyrin dimer **fp3_{Br}** (0.74 mg, 0.14 μ mol) and *S*-(4-ethynylphenyl)-thioacetate (0.25 mg, 1.4 μ mol) were dissolved in toluene (1 mL), DIPA (0.2 mL) was added and the solution was frozen in liquid nitrogen. Afterwards, tetrakis-triphenylphosphine palladium(0) (0.03 mg, 28 nmol) and CuI (0.005 mg, 28 nmol) were added and the mixture was evacuated. The solution was subjected to three freeze-pump-thaw cycles to exclude dioxygen, after which it was stirred at room temperature for 20 h. Then, more *S*-(4-ethynylphenyl)-thioacetate (0.25 mg, 1.4 μ mol) and tetrakis-triphenylphosphine palladium(0) (0.03 mg, 28 nmol) were added and stirring continued for 28 h. The mixture was directly passed over a SiO₂ plug eluted with DCM and the solvents removed. The product was purified by column chromatography (SiO₂, PE/DCM 4/1) and size exclusion chromatography (Biobeads SX-1, toluene + 1% pyridine). Yield: 0.58 mg, 78%. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.56 (d, J = 4.6 Hz, 4H), 7.80 (s, 4H), 7.79 (s, 8H), 7.76 (d, J = 8.2 Hz, 4H), 7.72 (s, 2H), 7.57 (s, 4H), 7.54 (d, J = 4.6 Hz, 4H), 7.48 (d, J = 8.2 Hz, 4H), 7.10 (s, 4H), 6.33 (s, 4H), 2.46 (s, 6H), 1.45 – 1.11 (m, 216H), 0.93 – 0.78 (m, 180H). UV-vis (CHCl₃) λ_{\max} / nm (ϵ / mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹): 1400 (226), 1243 (62.8), 718 (104), 672 (235), 436 (196), 358 (65.0). Molar absorption coefficients are corrected for silicone grease in the sample. MS (MALDI-TOF, dithranol) m/z : 5305.7 ([M]⁺ C₃₃₂H₅₁₆N₁₂O₂S₂Si₁₂Zn₃ requires 5305.1).

1.1 Electrochemistry.

Electrochemistry was performed in DCM with tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (0.1 M) as electrolyte at an analyte concentration of 0.1 mM. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded in a 3-electrode setup using a glassy carbon working electrode, a platinum wire counter electrode and a Ag|AgNO₃ (10 mM) reference electrode. Potentials were referenced vs. ferrocene by addition of ferrocene after the experiment. Table S1 gives an overview of the redox potentials for the compounds **FP2** and **FP3**. The electrochemical HOMO-LUMO gaps for these compounds are 1.08 V and 0.78 V, respectively.

Table S1. Redox potentials for compounds **FP2** and **FP3**.^a

Compound	$E_{1/2}(\text{red4})$	$E_{1/2}(\text{red3})$	$E_{1/2}(\text{red2})$	$E_{1/2}(\text{red1})$	$E_{1/2}(\text{ox1})$	$E_{1/2}(\text{ox2})$	$E_{1/2}(\text{ox3})$	$E_{1/2}(\text{ox4})$
FP2	n.d. ^b	n.d. ^b	-1.21	-1.01	0.07	0.49	0.95	n.d. ^b
FP3	-2.10	-1.80	-1.09	-0.93	-0.15	0.17	0.59	0.79

^a potentials vs. Fc|Fc⁺. ^b higher reduction / oxidation potentials were outside the solvent window.

Figure S2. Left: Cyclic voltammograms and Right: UV-vis-NIR spectra of the fused porphyrins **fp2** and **fp3**.

2. Break Junction Experiments

2.1. Sample preparation for single-molecule experiments. Each compound was deposited onto a freshly flame-annealed gold substrate from a 0.1–1.0 mM dichloromethane solution, using an immersion time of 30 minutes. After this time the substrate was removed and blown dry. To prepare the tip we mechanically cut a gold wire, rinse it with ethanol to remove any grease and then pass it briefly through a butane flame.

2.2. Single-Molecule Conductivity Studies. The conductance of each compound was measured using the STM-BJ method. All experiments were performed using a home-built STM, optimized for room temperature measurements in air. During the break-junction experiment, the tip is moved vertically in and out of contact with the substrate at a constant speed of approximately 10 nm/s, in 1 pm steps. For the conductance ($G = I/V$) versus distance measurements, a bias voltage V of between 0.1 and 0.2 V was applied between the tip and the substrate. A linear current-to-voltage converter with two amplification stages allows us to record conductance values over a large dynamic range which depends on the compound under investigation and chosen to explore the largest range of conductance according to the value of the histogram peak. We also place a resistor in series with the main circuit which limits the total current when the junction resistance is low. The size of the resistor depends on the gain used. Please see Table S2 for a table of gains and resistor used for each measurement.

The motion of the tip and the conductance measurement are controlled by an in-house computer program to record conductance versus tip-displacement (G vs. z) curves. Typically,

when moving out of contact, we move several nm after reaching our lower conductance limit. When in contact, the piezo moves a further 1–2 nm after reaching $1.0 G_0$. These limits guarantee that a broad gold contact is formed and broken in each cycle, and that any molecular junction is broken at the end of the cycle. We aim to carry out 5000–10000 approach and retraction cycles in each run, and we vary the location of the tip over the sample in order to avoid systematic errors in the data. We focus on the opening stages of the cycle. After data acquisition is complete, we first remove any blocks of traces in which there is a clear degradation in trace quality due (most likely) to tip blunting or excessive build-up of material between the electrodes. We then use an automated routine to separate traces displaying plateaus from those with tunnelling-only. This searches for regions of individual traces in which the conductance change is less than a certain amount across a minimum distance interval (for example, a plateau is identified when a $\Delta z > 0.1$ nm is needed to produce a change in conductance of $\Delta \log(G/G_0) < 0.1$ at any region below $0.5 G_0$). We use very similar criteria for all compounds.

2.3 I-V measurements. For the I-V measurements, we stop the piezo movement at defined points during the stretching of a single junction and perform a voltage ramp. This is done at set intervals (usually every 0.5 to 1 Å) during an opening trace (the precise number of I-V curves recorded depends on the length of the plateau). We aim to record several hundred molecular junctions, which generates about 10000 I-V curves, which is at the limit of what we can currently conveniently process. Between each two ramps (+V to -V and -V to +V), we return the voltage to the predetermined value and continue recording the current as the piezo is moved, thus allowing us to build a $G(z)$ trace as for the fixed-bias measurement.

Compound	Voltage (V) for Gz measurement	Gain 1/2	Series Resistor (Ω)
P1	0.2	$1.0 \times 10^7 / 5.0 \times 10^9$	205300
P2	0.2	$1.0 \times 10^7 / 5.0 \times 10^9$	1090000
P3	0.2	$5.0 \times 10^8 / 2.4 \times 10^{10}$	12000000
fP2	0.1	$4.9 \times 10^6 / 2.3 \times 10^8$	47500
fP3	0.1	$4.9 \times 10^6 / 2.3 \times 10^8$	47500

Table S2. Table of gains and series resistance values used for each measurement.

Figure S3. Examples of individual conductance plateaus for each molecule recorded at fixed bias. $V_{bias} = 0.2$ V for **P1/P2/P3** and 0.1 V for **fP2/fP3**.

Figure S4. 1D histograms for the fixed bias $G(z)$ measurements. $V_{bias} = 0.2$ V for **P1/P2/P3** and 0.1 V for **fP2/fP3**. Each histogram is normalised according to: $N_{norm} = N_{points} / n_{curves} / v_p / \Delta \log G$, where N_{points} is the number of points recorded in each bin, n_{curves} is the total number of G vs z curves included in the histogram, v_p is the number of points recorded per unit of length in z , and $\Delta \log G$ is the bin size.

Figure S5. 2D histograms for the fixed bias $G(z)$ measurements. A) **P3**. B) **P2**. C) **P1**. D) **fP2**. E) **fP3**. The number of junctions for each is: **P3**:1547 (17.3 %), **P2**: 2058 (29.0 %), **P1**: 1928 (16.8), **fP2**: 1733 (29.9 %), **fP3**: 589 (29.5 %). Only the plateau-containing traces are considered.

Figure S6. Comparison of 1D histograms obtained on the same sample for **fP3** using different gains.

2.4 Analysis of the standard deviation of the conductance in the G-V measurements

We notice that when repeating experiments with the same compound using fresh electrodes, the whole histogram peak can vary in position by between $\log(G/G_0) = 0.1\text{--}0.3$, despite similar numbers of junctions and overall percentages (see Figure S7 for an example with **P2**). This natural variability places limits on determining the ratio of conductance between any given set of molecules from single experimental runs. For the butadiyne series, the variation does not significantly alter the general large conductance decay with length. For the fused series, however, where there is a large degree of overlap in conductance across the whole series, these ratios will be more strongly affected by the fluctuations. We have analysed the uncertainty in the I-V measurements, thus, by dividing the results of the fixed bias measurements into smaller sets of G-z traces, representative of the number recorded during

the I-V measurement (ca. 200). We then plot the 1D histogram peak positions, as shown in Figure S8 for **P2** and S9 for **fp2**, and calculate the standard deviation from the mean. Figure S10 thus shows the mean $\log(G/G_0)$ -V curves for the fused series including the standard deviation.

Figure S7. Comparison of two separate measurements on **P2** using very similar gains with similar numbers of plateau-containing traces recorded (numbers given in figure). The overall percentage of these traces was also similar at 29.0 % (red histogram) and 28.6 % (black histogram). Fresh gold electrodes were used in both cases. The peak position of the black histogram lies at a value of $\log(G/G_0) = -5.34$. The red histogram is higher at $\log(G/G_0) = -5.21$.

Figure S8. Histogram peak positions obtained from the fixed bias $G(z)$ data for both runs of P2 broken down into smaller sets of consecutively recorded traces (approximately 100-200 in each). Mean peak position for run 1 = $4.6 \times 10^{-6} G_0$. Standard deviation = $9.0 \times 10^{-7} G_0$ (20 % of the mean). Mean peak position for run 2 = $6.1 \times 10^{-6} G_0$. Standard deviation = $1.4 \times 10^{-6} G_0$ (23 % of the mean).

Figure S9. a) Comparison of 1D histograms of differing numbers of individual plateau traces for fP2 between the fixed bias $G(z)$ (Figure 2) and IV measurements. b) Histogram peak positions obtained from the fixed bias $G(z)$ data for fP2 for smaller sets of plateau-containing traces. Each histogram contains 100-200 traces. Mean peak position = $1.13 \times 10^{-4} G_0$. Standard deviation = $1.7 \times 10^{-5} G_0$ (15 % of the mean).

Figure S10. $G(V)$ traces for **P1**, **fP2** and **fP3** including ± 1 standard deviation (derived from the larger data sets obtained from G_z -only measurements).

Figure S11. (a-e) 2D conductance-distance histograms for the butadiyne and fused series constructed from the traces in which IV data was collected. $N_{\text{junctions}} = 139$ (**P3**), 239 (**P2**) 177 (**P1**) 266 (**fP2**), 283 (**fP3**).

Figure S12. Plateau length histograms for (a) fused series and (b) butadiyne series. The length is measured for each trace between $0.5 G_0$ and the point at which the conductance drops to approximately one order of magnitude below the 1D conductance peak value. The vertical lines represent the calculated junction length taken as the distance between two Au atoms attached to both sulfur groups.

Figure S13. a) Example of an individual junction with IV ramps for **P1**. The red dots show where each IV was recorded. b) All IV curves recorded on this junction (plotted at $\log(G/G_0)$). c) Selected individual $\log(G/G_0)$ curves.

Figure S14. *a) Example of an individual junction with IV ramps for P2. The red dots show where each IV was recorded. b) All IV curves recorded on this junction (plotted at $\log(G/G_0)$). c) Selected individual $\log(G/G_0)$ curves.*

Figure S15. a) Example of an individual junction with IV ramps for **P3**. The red dots show where each IV was recorded. b) All IV curves recorded on this junction (plotted at $\log(G/G_0)$). c) Selected individual $\log(G/G_0)$ curves.

Figure S16. a) Example of an individual junction with IV ramps for fP2. The red dots show where each IV was recorded. b) All IV curves recorded on this junction (plotted at $\log(G/G_0)$). c) Selected individual $\log(G/G_0)$ curves.

Figure S17. *a)* Example of an individual junction with IV ramps for **fP3**. The red dots show where each IV was recorded. *b)* All IV curves recorded on this junction (plotted at $\log(G/G_0)$). *c)* Selected individual $\log(G/G_0)$ curves.

Figure S18. (a) $\ln(G)$ versus l plots for the C4 series at different bias voltages. (b) β - V .

Figure S19. a) $G(V)$ measurement keeping the bias voltage below 0.8 V (taken from Figure 2 *j* of the main text). b) $G(V)$ measurement on the same sample, but with the voltage range increased to ± 1.2 V (the number of junctions was 179 and the number of IV measurements was 6783).

Figure S20. Examples of individual junctions showing ‘U’ shaped (parabolic) $G(V)$ curves when the voltage is ramped between ± 1.0 V.

Figure S21. Examples of individual junctions showing complex, non-parabolic, shaped $G(V)$ curves when the voltage is ramped between ± 1.0 V.

Figure S22. Further examples of individual junctions showing complex, non-parabolic, shaped $G(V)$ (voltage = ± 1.2 V).

Figure S23. Comparison of two separate runs of *fP3* with freshly deposited molecules and different electrodes. In both runs IVs were recorded over a range of ± 0.8 V. a) Run 1 – as shown in the main text. b) Run 2 $N_{traces} = 289$.

Figure S24. Comparison of the $G(V)$ curves between different runs for the voltage range ± 0.8 V. a) Run 1. b). Run 2 all $G(V)$ curves (9658 curves). c). Run 2 showing only clearly ‘U’ shaped curves (1979 curves).

Figure S25. Examples of $G(V)$ switching behaviour for a single junction. The top panel shows the $G(z)$ conductance plateau (data points recorded at 0.1 V). The lower panel shows

G(V) curves recorded sequentially (starting from the top left and working across and down). The junction starts off with the G(V) curves displaying a dip about zero bias, and a relatively flat profile at higher bias. Then at some point the profile changes to a more parabolic ‘U’ shape, and proceeds to oscillate between the two states.

3. Tight Binding Model Details

In this section, we describe a simple tight binding model to capture the essential features of the butadiyne-linked wires. In this model, we treat each porphyrin ring as a single hopping site, ε , coupled through a hopping element γ (see Figure S26 for a schematic illustration). The two thiophenol anchor groups are represented by the sites labelled ε_L and ε_R respectively, which are linked to the electrodes through the couplings Γ_L and Γ_R , and to the (porphyrin) bridge sites through t_0 (see Section 3 in the SI for further details). The Hamiltonian of the central (molecular) part (\mathbf{H}_C) takes the following form for each compound:

$$H_{P1} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_L & t_0 & 0 \\ t_0 & \varepsilon_1 & t_0 \\ 0 & t_0 & \varepsilon_R \end{bmatrix}$$

$$H_{P2} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_L & t_0 & 0 & 0 \\ t_0 & \varepsilon_1 & \gamma & 0 \\ 0 & \gamma & \varepsilon_2 & t_0 \\ 0 & 0 & t_0 & \varepsilon_R \end{bmatrix}$$

$$H_{P3} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_L & t_0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ t_0 & \varepsilon_1 & \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \gamma & \varepsilon_2 & \gamma & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma & \varepsilon_3 & t_0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & t_0 & \varepsilon_R \end{bmatrix}$$

Where ε_1 , ε_2 and ε_3 are the energies of each bridge site (where the subscript refers to the site number), coupled to each other via a hopping element γ . ε_0 is the energy of the interface levels, coupled to the bridge sites through t_0 . The transmission as a function of energy (E) is given by

$$T(E) = 4\Gamma_L\Gamma_R|G_{LR}|^2 \quad (1)$$

where G_{LR} is the (1,3)/(1,4)/(1,5) term, respectively, of the Green's function

$$\mathbf{G} = [E\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{H}_C - \mathbf{\Sigma}]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

and $\mathbf{\Sigma} = \mathbf{\Sigma}_L + \mathbf{\Sigma}_R$, with $\mathbf{\Sigma}_L$ and $\mathbf{\Sigma}_R$ being the self-energies for left and right leads respectively, while $\mathbf{1}$ is the identity matrix.

$$\beta(E) = \frac{2}{R_0} \ln\left(\frac{\Delta E(E)}{\gamma}\right) \quad (3)$$

In this model we assume transport takes place through occupied levels due to the presence of thiol anchor groups. All parameters were kept the same for each compound (see the figures below for the precise values used in each case) where Γ_L , Γ_R , ϵ_L , ϵ_R and t_0 were chosen to give closest agreement with the experimental conductance, and which themselves do not influence the degree of attenuation in the off-resonant regime (Figure S29). To a first approximation, we can assume γ to equal the shift in the electrochemical (EC) oxidation potential between the monomer and dimer compounds. Based on the values in reference 9 we set γ to be 0.04 eV. In order to choose an appropriate value for the on-site energies of the porphyrin units we note that the EC HOMO-LUMO gap of the monomer is 2.1eV. If the Fermi level, E_F , (located at 0 eV in the model) sits in the centre of the H-L gap, ϵ would equal roughly -1 eV. Considering that the gap is expected to shrink slightly upon binding to gold due to image charge effects, we expect it would be slightly closer than this to E_F . It cannot be closer than about -0.5 eV as we observe no indication of reaching resonance by 1 V for **P1**. Thiols are also expected to shift E_F closer to the HOMO states, so based on these considerations we find setting ϵ to -0.8 eV a reasonable assumption.

The results of the T.B model using the values of γ obtained from EC are shown in Figure S27. The derived zero-bias β value is 4.0 nm^{-1} , which is about a factor 1.5-2 larger than in the experiments. Looking at the transmission curves, it is clear that there is an exponential conductance decay over a wide range of energies. To demonstrate this further, we have calculated I-V curves by integrating the transmission curves in Figure S27a. These are shown in Figure S27b (plotted as $\log(G/G_0)$). We cannot expect a completely quantitative comparison, particularly as we are not considering the effect of temperature, and neither can we be sure that E_F is the same for all compounds. We find the best agreement with the experiments by setting γ to equal 0.17 eV (Figure S28) and slightly reducing Γ (Figure S28).

Using the calculated I-V curves, we can also plot β as a function of bias voltage (Figure S30) and compare these with the experimental results. It is clear that regardless of exact the value of γ , the variation of β with bias voltage is well reproduced by the simple model. As only γ , ϵ and R_0 (the inter-site distance) determine β in this model (equation 3²), this allows us to predict the effect of changes to the chemical structure of the bridge. For example, increasing the coupling between bridge sites (whilst keeping the same spacing) will lower β , as will shifting the on-site energies closer to E_F (by chemical substitution for example). This is clearly manifested, at least qualitatively, in the results of the fused series, where the inter-ring coupling is dramatically increased (despite a small reduction in inter-site distance). Accurate modelling of the fused wires, however, would require the presence of both HOMO and LUMO states (as we have in our DTF calculations) due to the much smaller size of the H-L gap.

Figure S26. Scheme showing the simple model used to understand the voltage dependence of β in the C4 series.

Figure S27. (a) Transmission curves calculated from the model using the following parameters: $\varepsilon = -0.8$ eV, $\gamma = 0.04$ eV, $\varepsilon_L = \varepsilon_R = -0.8$ eV, $t_0 = 0.1$ eV, $\Gamma_L = \Gamma_R = 0.5$ eV. (b) $\text{Log}(G/G_0)$ -V curves from the model derived by integrating the transmission curves in a.

Figure S28. (a) Transmission curves calculated from the model using the following parameters: $\varepsilon = -0.8$ eV, $\gamma = 0.17$ eV, $\varepsilon_L = \varepsilon_R = -0.8$ eV, $t_0 = 0.1$ eV, $\Gamma_L = \Gamma_R = 0.3$ eV. (b) Log(G/G_0)-V curves from the model derived by integrating the transmission curves in a.

Figure S29. Comparison of transmission curves using the same parameters as in Figure S28, but changing Γ from 0.3 eV to 0.08 eV.

Figure S30. Experimental and TB-derived β -V curves for the C4 series.

4. DFT calculations for molecules P1, P2, P3, fP2, fP3

DFT quantum transport method: To theoretically model the conductance of the series of porphyrin molecules attached to gold electrodes we use a first principles quantum transport approach, combining the density functional code SIESTA³ and GOLLUM.⁴ Firstly, the optimum geometry of the isolated molecule was calculated using a double-zeta polarized basis set, an energy cutoff of 150 Rydbergs, norm conserving pseudopotentials and the GGA⁵ functional to describe the exchange correlation functional. The molecule was relaxed until all forces on the atoms were less than 0.1 V/Å. Gold electrodes were then attached to the molecule, which consisted of 7 layers of (111) gold each containing 16 atoms and the surface of the lead were constructed of a pyramidal tip to approximate the nature of the electrodes formed in the STM based experiment. The optimum binding location was found by relaxing the molecule in the presence of the gold leads and the gold-sulphur bond distance was found

to be 2.6 Å and the Au-S-C bond angle 140°. The zero bias transmission coefficient $T(E)$ was calculated by extracting a Hamiltonian describing this molecular junction (Figure S31) from SIESTA and utilizing the Greens function based method of GOLLUM. The conductance was then calculated from $G = I/V$ where $I = \int_{E_F - \frac{eV}{2}}^{E_F + \frac{eV}{2}} T(E) dE$.

Figure S31. *Geometry of molecule P1 contacted between gold electrodes*

Frontier Orbitals

	HOMO-1	HOMO	LUMO	LUMO+1
P1	 -2.33eV			
fP2	 -2.47eV			
fP3	 -2.63eV			
P2	 -2.45eV			
P3	 -2.68eV			

Figure S32. Structure of the porphyrins **P1**, **P2**, **P3**, **fP2** and **fP3** and the corresponding frontier HOMO- LUMO orbitals calculated by DFT.

Transmission calculations

Figure S33 shows the uncorrected zero bias transmission coefficient $T(E)$ for molecules **P1**, **P2** and **P3**. The DFT-predicted Fermi energy E_F^0 lies close to the HOMO resonances which is typical behaviour in thiol anchored molecules. At this Fermi energy the conductance is overestimated, which is a well-known problem in DFT based quantum transport calculations⁶ as it underestimates the size of the HOMO LUMO gap. To correct this, we apply a ‘scissor’ correction to the transmission calculation so that the gap between the HOMO and LUMO resonances match the experimental electrochemical gaps, which are measured as follows: **P1** -2.08V, **P2** -1.9V, **P3** -1.8V, **fP2** -1.08V and **fP3** -0.78V. The Fermi energy E_F^- is then fitted to each individual trace to give the best agreement with the experimental conductance-voltage curves. It is the transmission curves in Figure S33b and d which are used to generate the G vs Voltage curves shown in Figure 4b of the main paper.

Figure S33. DFT transmission coefficient of a) butadiyne-linked porphyrin b) scissor corrected butadiyne-linked porphyrin c) fused porphyrin d) scissor corrected fused porphyrin for the lengths $N = 1, 2$ and 3.

Ionization Potential and Electron affinity

The Ionization Potential (IP) and electron affinity (EA) of the series of molecules is calculated using the following formula: $IP = E(N-1) - E(N)$ and $EA = E(N) - E(N+1)$, where E is the ground state energy of the molecule and N is the number of electrons. In this case the values are calculated in the gas phase with the thiol anchor groups maintaining their hydrogen atom, which is not the case when the molecules are contacted to gold electrodes.

	IP (eV)	EA (eV)
P1	5.19	1.26
P2	4.86	1.85
P3	4.69	2.12
fp2	4.40	2.40
fp3	4.26	2.65

Table S3. Calculated ionization potentials and electron affinities for the porphyrin series.

DFT-based Beta Factor calculation

Figure S34. Calculated versus experimental beta factor for C4 series (upper - green) and fused (lower - blue).

5. References

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